

**Fatigue lifetime of both plain and notched components made of
additively manufactured AISI 316L**

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ABSTRACT

During last few years, the Additive Manufacturing (AM) technology has increasingly attracted the interest of both industries and researchers. In such a context, the present paper deals with the analysis of specimens made of additively manufactured AISI 316L stainless steel subjected to cyclic loading. More precisely, fatigue tests available in the literature and related to both plain and notched specimens are considered. The fatigue assessment of such specimens is performed by means of an analytical methodology, recently proposed by the present authors, consisting of the joint application of: a multiaxial stress-based fatigue criterion, named Carpinteri et al. criterion, which exploits the concept of the critical plane, and a stress averaging method, named Critical Direction Method, for the determination of the orientation of the critical plane. Satisfactory results are here obtained in terms of

fatigue life for AM components, irrespective of both the specimen geometry and the degree of multiaxiality and non-proportionality.

KEYWORDS: AM metallic specimens; analytical methodology; fatigue life; notched specimen; stress-based criterion; uniaxial/biaxial loading

1. INTRODUCTION

Additive Manufacturing (AM) is an automatic technique for the realization of mechanical components by adding successive layers of material according to 3D-model data. It is considered one of the most innovative manufacturing techniques, having the potentiality to contribute to continuous innovation in different industrial fields, such as biomedical, aerospace, automotive, packaging and construction [1].

AM is characterised by many advantages with respect to the traditional manufacturing techniques [2]. In particular, it allows the realization of customized structural components characterised by complex geometries, which would be difficult or even not possible to obtain through traditional processes. Moreover, a considerable low material waste is produced by AM, which can thus be considered a sustainable technique.

Nowadays, AM allows to realize components intended for different uses and made of many materials that is, polymers, composites, concretes and metals [3-7]. Narrowing the field to the latter ones, different alloys, such as Ti-, Ni- and Al-based alloys, are effectively realized, as well as different stainless steels.

In such a context, different types of AM processes can be distinguished on the basis of the raw material employed (fine powders or wires), the nature of the power source (laser or electron beam), and the energy source (laser powder bed fusion or direct energy deposition) [8]. Among them, Selective Laser Melting (SLM) is the most commonly used technique for metals additively manufacturing,

since it is able to guarantee an efficient reproduction of complex geometries with high precision and a relatively good surface quality, as well as an effective low consumption of raw material [9].

However, in the field of AM there are still several open challenges related to the uncertainty on structural performance, especially under complex cyclic loadings typical of in-service conditions [10]. As a matter of fact, although from the point of view of static mechanical properties both AM and traditional metals behave in a similar manner, the same thing does not apply to the fatigue performances, which appear reduced in case of AM components, both in LCF and HCF regimes. This peculiarity is a consequence of internal defects, residual stresses, significant surface roughness and material anisotropy, which are related to the specific manufacturing process. These critical issues can be slightly mitigated, but surely not eliminated, by adjusting the printing parameters [11].

In order to significantly counteract the above disadvantages, the AM components can be subjected to post-manufacturing treatments [12]. In particular, surface treatments (such as sandblasting, shot peening, laser shock peening, machining) can be employed to improve the surface finish and to eventually introduce a superficial compressive residual stress field, in order to inhibit surface crack initiation [13]. On the other hand, standard heat treatments (such as annealing) and innovative heat treatments (such as hot isostatic pressing) are able to almost eliminate both tensile residual stress

and internal defects, as well as to homogenize the material microstructure [14].

In such a context, although several research works have been published with the aim to deeply investigate the fatigue behaviour of AM metals from an experimental point of view [15,16], only few attempts of theoretical investigations have been performed. Therefore, nowadays the goal of the research in the AM field is still to find and validate criteria for the fatigue assessment, in order to more exploit the use of such a powerful manufacturing technique. In this regard, it has been found that critical plane-based criteria represent a valid tool for the fatigue assessment of AM metals [17].

In the present paper, an analytical methodology [18-21], recently proposed by the present authors for metallic components subjected to fretting fatigue, is extended to the case of AM components. Such a methodology consists of the joint application of: a multiaxial stress-based fatigue criterion, named Carpinteri et al. criterion [22-25], which exploits the concept of the critical plane, and a stress averaging method, named Critical Direction Method [26,27], for the determination of the orientation of the critical plane.

An experimental campaign, available in the literature [17] and carried out on additively manufactured AISI 316L stainless steel subjected to cyclic loading, is analysed by employing the above methodology. More precisely, fatigue tests related to both plain specimens and specimens characterised by either sharp, circular or blunt notch are considered.

The present paper is structured as follows. **Section 2** is devoted to the description of the methodology employed for the fatigue assessment of traditional metallic components in presence of a stress concentration. Then, the experimental campaign analysed is summarised in **Section 3**. The results obtained by applying the above methodology to both plain and notched specimens are discussed in **Sections 4** and **5**, respectively. Finally, some conclusions are drawn in **Section 6**.

2. A CRITICAL PLANE-BASED ANALYTICAL METHODOLOGY FOR FATIGUE ASSESSMENT IN PRESENCE OF A STRESS CONCENTRATION

This Section deals with the description of the main steps of the analytical methodology adopted for the fatigue assessment of metallic structures in presence of a stress concentration. Note that the same methodology has been recently proposed by the present authors [18-21] for the case of fretting affected metallic components, providing satisfactory results in terms of both crack path orientation and fatigue life estimations. Consequently, due to the so-called analogy between fretting fatigue and notch fatigue [28], such a methodology is here applied for the first time to notch components.

This methodology is based on:

- (i) a multiaxial fatigue criterion, named Carpinteri et al. criterion [22-25], for the fatigue parameter computation and the fatigue life assessment;

(ii) a stress averaging method, named Critical Direction Method [26,27], for the determination of the orientation of the critical plane.

Moreover, this methodology takes into account a parameter related to the material microstructure, that is, the average grain size of the material, d .

The algorithm of such a methodology is shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1.

Firstly, some *input data* need to be defined, that is: the geometric sizes characterising the notched component, the loading conditions and the mechanical and fatigue properties of the material.

Then, the *stress field* within the structural component is computed, and the *hot-spot* (that is, the point on the material surface where the crack is assumed to nucleate) is defined on the surface of the component itself.

Successively, the *critical plane orientation* is determined (see the grey block in **Figure 1**) according to the procedure hereafter detailed (see **Figure 2**), which is based on the Critical Direction Method [26,27]. In particular, material planes passing through the hot-spot and characterised by different orientations α (measured with respect to the notch bisector) are considered. Note that a suitable angular increment, $\Delta\alpha$, between two different material planes needs to be set.

Figure 2.

Initially, an orientation equal to zero is assumed (first critical plane candidate). Then, the stress components acting on the corresponding plane are computed in different equally spaced points, from the hot-spot and moving inside the component along the plane itself, up to a length equal to twice the average grain size of the material, $2d$. Such stress components, averaged along the critical plane candidate, are employed for the computation of the fatigue parameter, $N_{eq,a}(\alpha)$, related to the considered orientation. In accordance with the Carpinteri et al. criterion [22-25], such a fatigue parameter is defined as:

$$N_{eq,a}(\alpha) = \bar{N}_a(\alpha) + \sigma_{af,-1} \left(\frac{\bar{N}_m(\alpha)}{\sigma_u} \right) \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{N}_a(\alpha)$ and $\bar{N}_m(\alpha)$ are the values (averaged along the critical plane candidate) of the amplitude and the mean value of the normal stress component acting on the critical plane, respectively, $\sigma_{af,-1}$ is the fully-reversed normal stress fatigue strength referred to N_0 loading cycles, and σ_u is the ultimate tensile strength.

Then, a new orientation is taken into account (that is, another critical plane candidate is considered), and the procedure is iterated for all material planes inward the component (that is, for $-90^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 90^\circ$). The orientation, α_{cr} , that produces the maximum value of the above fatigue parameter, $N_{eq,a}(\alpha_{cr})$, is defined as the critical plane.

Finally, the *fatigue assessment* of the component analysed is performed (see the blue block in **Figure 1**) by employing the stress components acting on the critical plane at the verification point, P_{cr} , which is located on the critical plane at a distance from the hot-spot equal to twice the average grain size of the material, $2d$. More in detail, the fatigue life, N_{cal} , is computed according to the Carpinteri et al. criterion [22-25], by iteratively solving the following equation:

$$\sqrt{\left[N_{eq,a}(\alpha_{cr},2d)\right]^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{af,-1}}{\tau_{af,-1}}\right)^2 \left(\frac{N_{cal}}{N_0}\right)^{2m} \left(\frac{N_0}{N_{cal}}\right)^{2m^*} \left[C_a(\alpha_{cr},2d)\right]^2} = \sigma_{af,-1} \left(\frac{N_{cal}}{N_0}\right)^{2m} \quad (2)$$

where $\tau_{af,-1}$ is the fully-reversed shear stress fatigue strength referred to N_0 loading cycles, m and m^* are the slopes of the S-N curves under fully-reversed normal and shear loading, respectively, C_a is the amplitude of the shear stress component lying on the critical plane, and $N_{eq,a}(\alpha_{cr},2d)$ is given by:

$$N_{eq,a}(\alpha_{cr},2d) = N_a(\alpha_{cr},2d) + \sigma_{af,-1} \left(\frac{N_m(\alpha_{cr},2d)}{\sigma_u} \right) \quad (3)$$

It is important to highlight that, in case of plain fatigue (that is, without notches), the grey block in **Figure 1** is not passed and the Critical Direction Method is not applied. As a matter of fact, the *critical plane orientation* is determined according to the original formulation of the Carpinteri et al. criterion [22-25]. Moreover, in such a condition the verification point P_{cr} , where to perform the *fatigue assessment* of the component analysed, coincides with the hot-spot on the material surface.

3. EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN EXAMINED

The present Section deals with the description of the experimental campaign carried out by Wang et al. [17] on additively manufactured AISI 316L stainless steel subjected to cyclic loading. More precisely, fatigue tests related to both plain specimens and notched specimens are considered. The manufacturing process, the material properties and the specimens' geometry are reported in the following, as well as the testing setup, the loading configurations and the experimental results.

All the specimens were made of AISI 316L stainless steel, additively manufactured by means of the Selective Laser Melting (SLM) technology. The process parameters employed were: a laser power equal to 450 W, a scan speed equal to 1500–2000 mm/s and a scan pitch equal to 0.05 mm.

Subsequently, a post-manufacturing heat treatment was performed in order to significantly reduce both the microstructure anisotropy and inhomogeneity. In particular, the 3D-printed rods made of AM AISI 316L stainless steel were annealed at a temperature equal to 490 °C for 6 h, and subsequently subjected to a cooling process employing argon.

Finally, each specimen was machined from the AM annealed rods by means of a conventional lathe, in order to guarantee a high level of surface finishing.

The mechanical properties after the above manufacturing process were experimentally determined, that is: elastic modulus, $E=191GPa$; Poisson's coefficient, $\nu=0.3$; yield stress, $\sigma_y=380MPa$; and ultimate tensile strength, $\sigma_u=642MPa$. The fatigue properties were also determined according to the recommendations of the International Institute of Welding for welded metals [29]: the fully-reversed normal and shear stress fatigue strengths were found to be $\sigma_{af,-1}=249MPa$ and $\tau_{af,-1}=216MPa$, respectively, in correspondence of a number of loading cycles to failure $N_0=2\cdot 10^6$, and the slope of the S-N curves under fully-reversed normal and shear stress were $m=15.3$ and $m^*=32.7$, respectively.

Moreover, as far as the material microstructure is concerned, the average grain size, d , can be computed from the values reported in Ref. [30], by exploiting the procedure reported in Ref. [31]. In particular, a value of $d=48\mu m$ is obtained.

Four different specimen types were manufactured, that is: plain specimens, specimens with a sharp notch (root radius $\rho=0.07mm$), specimens with a circular notch (root radius $\rho=2mm$) and specimens with a blunt notch (root radius $\rho=5mm$). The geometry of both plain specimens and specimens characterised by sharp, circular and blunt notches is shown in **Figures 3(a)-(d)**, respectively.

Figure 3.

All the specimens were subjected to fatigue tests by means of an MTS 809 axial/torsional testing machine. Pure axial, pure torsional and biaxial (that is, combined axial-torsional) tests were carried out under force/moment control. Note that, although both constant and variable amplitude fatigue tests were carried out, the present work only focuses on the constant amplitude ones. Such tests were characterised by a fatigue loading ratio, R , equal to either 0 or -1, and different stress levels were considered. Moreover, in the case of biaxial tests, both in-phase (phase shift $\beta=0^\circ$ between axial and torsional loading) and out-of-phase (phase shift $\beta=90^\circ$ between axial and torsional loading) configurations were tested.

The experimental number of loading cycles to failure, N_{exp} , was assumed as the number of loading cycles in correspondence of the nucleation of visible cracks, characterised by a length equal to about 1 mm. Moreover, the run-out condition was set at $2 \cdot 10^6$ loading cycles. It is worth noting that during the experimental campaign the run-out specimens were re-tested, due to the high manufacturing cost. The re-tested specimens are not taken into account in the present study, since they are characterised by a high uncertainty in terms of fatigue life due to the previous load history.

The loading configurations of plain specimens, sharp notched specimens, circular notched specimens and blunt notched specimens are detailed in **Tables 1-4**, respectively, where the amplitudes of the applied axial stress, σ , and shear stress, τ , the fatigue loading ratio, R , and the phase shift, β , are listed. The experimental number of loading cycles to failure, N_{exp} , is also

present in such Tables for each tested specimen (run-outs are marked with *).

Table 1.

Table 2.

Table 3.

Table 4.

4. METHODOLOGY APPLICATION TO AM PLAIN SPECIMENS

In the present Section the AM plain specimens tested by Wang et al. [17] and described in **Section 3** are analysed. In particular, the methodology detailed in **Section 2** is employed in order to perform the fatigue assessment of such specimens. Some basic assumptions are pointed out in **Sub-Section 4.1**, whereas **Sub-Section 4.2** is devoted to describe and comment the results obtained.

4.1 Basic assumptions

In order to simulate the experimental plain fatigue tests [17] described in **Section 3** by means of the analytical methodology here proposed (see **Section 2**), some remarks are needed. As a matter of fact, such a methodology is based on the Carpinteri et al. criterion [22-25], that is, a stress-based fatigue criterion originally devised to perform the fatigue assessment of traditional metallic materials, which can be thought of as homogeneous and isotropic [32]. However, such a criterion can be applied to the above experimental

data since a proper post-manufacturing heat treatment process was performed [17]. More in detail, the specimens were subjected to an annealing process, which is able to significantly reduce both the microstructure anisotropy and inhomogeneity [10,33].

According to the above remarks, the examined additively manufactured AISI 316L stainless steel can be treated as homogeneous and isotropic.

Furthermore, due to the above heat treatment, the tensile residual stresses generated during the AM fabrication process can be considered completely relaxed [17]. Consequently, such residual stresses are not taken into account in the present analysis.

Finally, regarding the surface roughness, it is well known that it represents a major concern in high cycle fatigue problems, where most of the life is spent in initiating a crack [34]. However, since the AM specimens here analysed were machined by using a conventional lathe, taking particular care to reach a high level of surface finishing, the influence of the surface roughness on the fatigue behaviour of such specimens is hereafter neglected.

Consequently, according to the above remarks, the Carpinteri et al. criterion [22-25] can be employed to theoretically perform the fatigue life assessment of the examined AM plain specimens.

Finally, it is worth noting that the hot-spot on the material surface is here assumed in correspondence of the middle-cross section of the specimen.

4.2 Results and discussion

The fatigue life assessment of the experimental plain fatigue tests, available in the literature [17] and described in **Section 3**, is here performed by employing the analytical methodology described in **Section 2**.

The calculated number of loading cycles to failure, N_{cal} , is plotted in **Figure 4** against the corresponding experimental value, N_{exp} , for each loading configuration examined, where the dashed lines represent the scatter band with factor of 2 and the dot-dashed lines represent the scatter band with factor of 3. Moreover, N_{cal} values are also listed in **Table 1** for each tested specimen.

Figure 4.

From the above graphs it is possible to observe that the applied methodology provides satisfactory results, mainly falling within the scatter band with factor 2. More precisely, all the results fall within the scatter band 2 in case of axial loading, with both loading ratio $R=-1$ (**Figure 4(a)**) and $R=0$ (**Figure 4(b)**), and torsional loading, with loading ratio $R=-1$ (**Figure 4(c)**). Moreover, in case of biaxial loading, 43% of the results fall within the scatter band 2, whereas 86% within the scatter band 3. Moreover, it can be noted that, although the estimation related to the case of biaxial loading with loading ratio $R=-1$ and phase angle $\beta=90^\circ$ is not in good agreement with the experimental results, it is on the conservative side.

The quality of the present results can be statistically interpreted by employing the root mean square error method [35,36]. In particular, the root mean square error, T_{RMS} , is computed as follows:

$$T_{RMS} = 10 \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \log^2(N_{cal}/N_{exp})_j}{n}} \quad (4)$$

where n is the number of the examined fatigue data. As a matter of fact, a root mean square error equal to 1 indicates perfect correlation between experimental results and analytical estimations.

The T_{RMS} values related to the present analytical methodology are listed in **Table 5** for plain fatigue tests. The results, available in the literature [17] and obtained by employing a different critical plane-based multiaxial fatigue criterion, named Maximum Wöhler Curve Method (MWCM), are also reported for comparison. In particular, a T_{RMS} value is computed for each loading configuration here examined, that is, axial with both $R=-1$ and $R=0$, torsional with $R=-1$ and biaxial fatigue loading. In addition, an overall value is determined relatively to all the plain fatigue tests. Note that, run-outs tests are not considered in the T_{RMS} evaluation.

Table 5.

The analysis of the results in terms of the mean square error clearly indicates that:

- in case of both pure axial and pure torsional loading, quite accurate results are here obtained, since the values of T_{RMS} are lower than 2;

- in case of biaxial loading, a higher value of T_{RMS} is obtained. However, in such a case, statistical considerations are quite unreliable due to the very small number of specimens for each loading configuration;

- for all fatigue tests, similar accuracy is noticed by using the present methodology and the MWCM criterion; in general, a higher accuracy is gained by applying the present methodology, with a decrease of the T_{RMS} overall value equal to 12% with respect to that deduced through the MWCM criterion.

Therefore, it can be concluded that a high level of accuracy is obtained by employing the present analytical methodology, in terms of fatigue life assessment of plain specimens made of the examined additively manufactured AISI 316L stainless steel. As a matter of fact, a T_{RMS} overall value lower than 2 is obtained in such a case.

5. METHODOLOGY APPLICATION TO AM NOTCHED SPECIMENS

In the present Section the AM notched specimens tested by Wang et al. [17] and described in **Section 3** are analysed. In particular, the analytical methodology described in **Section 2** is employed in order to perform the fatigue assessment of such specimens. In **Sub-Section 5.1** some basic assumptions are pointed out and some

theoretical concepts are referred to, whereas **Sub-Section 5.2** is devoted to describe and comment the results obtained.

5.1 Basic assumptions and theoretical concepts

In order to simulate the experimental notch fatigue tests [17] summarised in **Section 3**, by means of the analytical methodology described in **Section 2**, some remarks are needed. As a matter of fact, such a methodology employs the Carpinteri et al. criterion for the fatigue assessment and, consequently, the same basic assumptions considered for additively manufactured AISI 316L stainless steel in the case of plain fatigue (see **Sub-Section 4.1**) need to be taken in mind also in the case of notch fatigue. In particular:

(a) the examined additively manufactured AISI 316L stainless steel can be treated as homogeneous and isotropic due to the post-manufacturing heat treatment process performed [17];

(b) the tensile residual stresses generated during the AM fabrication process are not taken into account in the present analysis since they are completely relaxed due to the above heat treatment;

(c) the influence of the surface roughness on the fatigue behaviour of the specimens analysed is here neglected, since a high level of surface finishing was ensured by using a conventional lathe [17].

Furthermore, regarding the methodology here employed and presented in details in **Section 2**, some theoretical concepts need to be emphasized. In particular, the stress state within the AM

component is computed by means of a set of closed-form expressions available in the literature [37,38]. It is worth noting that the closed form solutions here employed may be used to determine the overall stress field in both sharp and blunt notched components subjected to axial [37] and torsion [38] loading. In particular, such analytical solutions were derived by imposing global equilibrium conditions and formulated by means of complex potential functions and the actual notch shape. More details about the analytical solutions here employed can be found in Refs. [39-41].

It is important to stress that, in order to apply the above closed-form expressions, some characteristic parameters related to the notch geometry and the remote loading conditions need to be set. Among such parameters, the stress concentration factors, K_t , characterising each test configuration examined have been taken from the corresponding diagrams available in Ref. [42] and are here listed in **Table 6**. Note that the K_t value for a V-shaped notched bar of circular cross section is obtained in accordance with the procedure proposed in Ref. [42] that is, by multiplying the K_t value related to a flat tension bar with opposite V-shaped notches by the ratio of the Neuber three-dimensional K_t over two-dimensional K_t values in presence of hyperbolic notches [43].

Table 6.

Finally, it is worth noting that the hot-spot on the material surface is here assumed to coincide with the point experiencing the

largest magnitude of the local linear-elastic stresses, that is the notch root. In other words, the crack nucleation process is expected in correspondence with the notch root, in accordance with the experimental observations [17] of fatigue cracks emanating always from the notch tip region.

5.2 Results and discussion

The fatigue assessment of the experimental notch fatigue tests, available in the literature [17] and described in **Section 3**, is here performed by employing the analytical methodology described in **Section 2**.

The calculated number of loading cycles to failure, N_{cal} , is plotted in **Figures 5, 6 and 7** against the corresponding experimental value, N_{exp} , for each loading configuration examined, in case of sharp notch with a root radius $\rho=0.07mm$, circular notch with a root radius $\rho=2mm$ and blunt notch with a root radius $\rho=5mm$, respectively. Moreover, N_{cal} values are also listed in **Tables 2-4** for each tested specimen with sharp notch, circular notch and blunt notch, respectively.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

It is possible to point out that the applied methodology provides satisfactory results, since in most cases the theoretical results

lie within the scatter bands 2 or 3, and this holding true irrespective of the notch type and the loading conditions.

Relatively to the case of sharp notch, 43% and 57% of the results fall within scatter band 2 and 3, respectively, in case of axial loading (**Figure 5(a)**). Moreover, in case of biaxial loading, nearly half of the results fall within scatter band 2 and more than 70% of the estimations are inside scatter band 3. The most satisfactory estimations are obtained in the case of out-of-phase biaxial loading with $R=-1$ (**Figure 5(c)**), all being within scatter band 2.

Relatively to the case of circular notch, half of the results fall within scatter band 2 in case of biaxial loading with a loading ratio $R=-1$ (**Figures 6(a)** and **(b)**). Such a value increases when biaxial loading with $R=0$ is considered, with 67% of the estimations in scatter band 2 for out-of-phase loading (**Figure 6(d)**) and 86% for in-phase loading (**Figure 6(c)**).

Relatively to the case of blunt notch, almost all the results fall within the scatter band 3. In particular, the most satisfactory estimations are obtained in the case of out-of-phase biaxial loading with $R=-1$ (**Figure 7(b)**), all being within scatter band 2.

The quality of the above results can be statistically interpreted by employing the root mean square error method [35,36] (see Eq. (4)). The T_{RMS} values related to the present analytical methodology are listed in **Table 7** for notch fatigue tests. In particular, a T_{RMS} value is computed for each loading configuration here examined. In addition, an overall value is determined relatively to each notch fatigue test type.

Table 7.

The analysis of the results in terms of the mean square error clearly indicates that quite accurate results are here obtained, since the overall values of T_{RMS} are lower than 3. Moreover, in the presence of blunt notch better estimations are provided by the present methodology with respect to the case of sharp notch. As a matter of fact, the level of accuracy obtained in the case of blunt notch with $\rho=5mm$ is comparable with that related to plain fatigue specimens (see **Sub-Section 4.2**), which are characterised by a T_{RMS} overall value equal to 1.98.

Furthermore, the level of accuracy that characterises each notch configuration appears to be almost independent of the load configuration. As a matter of fact, it is not possible to recognise a particular loading configuration associated to worse estimations with respect to the others. This fact confirms the robustness of the applied methodology, which is able to provide satisfactory results in terms of fatigue life assessment, irrespective of the degree of multiaxiality and non-proportionality.

Therefore, it can be concluded that a high level of accuracy is obtained by employing the present analytical methodology, in terms of fatigue life assessment of notched specimens made of the examined additively manufactured AISI 316L stainless steel. As a matter of fact, a T_{RMS} overall value approximately equal to 2 is obtained for

both blunt and circular notches, and a value lower than 3 for the case of sharp notch.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, the fatigue behaviour of AM metallic specimens under both uniaxial and biaxial cyclic loading has been theoretically examined. In particular, several fatigue tests, available in the literature and carried out on both plain and notched specimens made of AM AISI 316L stainless steel, have been simulated by means of the proposed analytical methodology, which is based on the stress-based multiaxial fatigue criterion by Carpinteri and co-workers and the Critical Direction Method.

Satisfactory results have been obtained in terms of fatigue life, irrespective of both the specimen geometry and the degree of multiaxiality and non-proportionality.

As far as plain specimens are concerned:

- estimations within scatter band 2 have been obtained for uniaxial loading, whereas more scattered, albeit conservative, results have been found for biaxial loading;
- an overall T_{RMS} value equal to 1.98 has been computed, thus highlighting a high level of accuracy from a statistical point of view;
- a higher accuracy has been gained by applying the present methodology with respect to that obtained by Wang et al. by

using the MWCM criterion, with a decrease of the T_{RMS} overall value equal to 12%.

As far as notched specimens are concerned:

- T_{RMS} overall values of 2.83, 2.21 and 1.95 have been obtained for the case of sharp, circular and blunt notches, respectively;
- the level of accuracy obtained in the case of blunt notch (with notch root $\rho=5mm$) is comparable with that related to plain fatigue specimens.

Based on such encouraging results, the validity of the present methodology is confirmed for AM materials. In particular, it can be considered as a promising engineering tool for fatigue design of AM metallic components in high-cycle fatigue regime. However, further research works need to be done in order to safely extend the use of such a methodology to other AM metals.

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NOMENCLATURE

C_a	amplitude of the shear stress component lying on the critical plane
d	average grain size of the material
E	elastic modulus
K_t	stress concentration factor
m	slope of the S-N curve under fully-reversed normal loading
m^*	slope of the S-N curve under fully-reversed shear loading
N_a	amplitude of the normal stress component acting on the critical plane
N_{cal}	fatigue life calculated through the present methodology
$N_{eq,a}$	amplitude of the equivalent normal stress related to the critical plane
N_{exp}	experimental number of loading cycles to failure
N_m	mean value of the normal stress component acting on the critical plane
N_0	reference number of loading cycles for fatigue strength values
P_{cr}	verification point
T_{RMS}	root mean square error
R	fatigue loading ratio
β	phase shift between axial and torsional loading
α	critical plane candidate orientation
α_{cr}	critical plane orientation
ν	Poisson's coefficient
ρ	root radius of the notch
$\sigma_{af,-1}$	fully-reversed normal stress fatigue strength
$\tau_{af,-1}$	fully-reversed shear stress fatigue strength

**Fatigue lifetime of both plain and notched components made of
additively manufactured AISI 316L**

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FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1. Flowchart of the analytical methodology for fatigue assessment in presence of notch.

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of the procedure for determining the critical plane orientation in presence of notch.

Figure 3. Geometry of (a) plain specimens and specimens characterised by (b) sharp, (c) circular and (d) blunt notches (sizes in mm).

Table 1. Loading configurations and both experimental, N_{exp} , and estimated, N_{cal} , fatigue life values (run-outs are marked with *) for the plain specimens.

TEST No.	σ [MPa]	τ [MPa]	R [-]	β [°]	N_{exp} [cycles]	N_{cal} [cycles]
T1	250.0	0.0	-1	-	1043051	1399830
T2	250.0	0.0	-1	-	1706842	1399830
T3	280.0	0.0	-1	-	412342	365058
T4	280.0	0.0	-1	-	618798	365058
T5	320.0	0.0	-1	-	36576	43254
T6	320.0	0.0	-1	-	68555	43254
T7	370.0	0.0	-1	-	4426	4694
T8	370.0	0.0	-1	-	3342	4694
T9	160.0	0.0	0	-	2004951*	9238157
T10	170.0	0.0	0	-	2005966*	4375618
T11	180.0	0.0	0	-	857648	1643281
T12	180.0	0.0	0	-	1998224*	1643321
T13	200.0	0.0	0	-	301913	275755
T14	200.0	0.0	0	-	205515	275755
T15	250.0	0.0	0	-	78135	40739
T16	250.0	0.0	0	-	73638	40739
T17	0.0	175.0	-1	-	2048693*	42414518
T18	0.0	220.0	-1	-	725325	565772
T19	0.0	230.0	-1	-	253198	216371
T20	0.0	230.0	-1	-	248347	216371
T21	0.0	240.0	-1	-	107185	81850
T22	0.0	240.0	-1	-	98958	81850
T23	0.0	255.0	-1	-	4850	9831
T24	0.0	255.0	-1	-	9924	9831
T25	220.0	127.0	-1	0.0	574909	192513
T26	230.0	132.8	-1	0.0	27722	81111
T27	220.0	127.0	-1	90.0	2000000*	145898

T28	230.0	132.8	-1	90.0	633473	56659
T29	175.0	101.0	0	0.0	155716	127876
T30	190.0	109.7	0	0.0	69511	41485
T31	175.0	101.0	0	90.0	160274	466059
T32	190.0	109.7	0	90.0	80828	131963

Table 2. Loading configurations and both experimental, N_{exp} , and estimated, N_{cal} , fatigue life values (run-outs are marked with *) for the specimens with a sharp notch (root radius $\rho=0.07mm$).

TEST No.	σ [MPa]	τ [MPa]	R [-]	β [°]	N_{exp} [cycles]	N_{cal} [cycles]
SN1	135.0	0.0	-1	-	2002710*	77275727
SN2	170.0	0.0	-1	-	1604731	5600635
SN3	195.0	0.0	-1	-	1044071	1164650
SN4	195.0	0.0	-1	-	486818	1164650
SN5	220.0	0.0	-1	-	91803	292657
SN6	220.0	0.0	-1	-	42955	292657
SN7	270.0	0.0	-1	-	39189	28033
SN8	270.0	0.0	-1	-	25396	28033
SN9	138.0	79.7	-1	0.0	2005448*	9078321
SN10	155.0	89.5	-1	0.0	2038392*	1834542
SN11	155.0	89.5	-1	0.0	575494	1834542
SN12	190.0	109.7	-1	0.0	400053	103658
SN13	190.0	109.7	-1	0.0	76709	103658
SN14	230.0	132.8	-1	0.0	30101	6034
SN15	230.0	132.8	-1	0.0	22265	6034
SN16	120.0	69.3	0	0.0	2007071*	1791750
SN17	120.0	69.3	0	0.0	2000000*	1791745
SN18	120.0	69.3	0	0.0	232778	1791745
SN19	130.0	75.1	0	0.0	516411	646925

SN20	130.0	75.1	0	0.0	1342918	646925
SN21	150.0	86.7	0	0.0	64657	96400
SN22	150.0	86.7	0	0.0	70912	96400
SN23	200.0	115.5	0	0.0	7924	1984
SN24	200.0	115.5	0	0.0	5928	1984
SN25	155.0	89.5	-1	90.0	2000042*	1595366
SN26	155.0	89.5	-1	90.0	1970361	1595366
SN27	190.0	109.7	-1	90.0	36165	53724
SN28	190.0	109.7	-1	90.0	101949	53724
SN29	120.0	69.3	0	90.0	2004041*	4054961
SN30	120.0	69.3	0	90.0	847439	4054961
SN31	130.0	75.1	0	90.0	939062	1304592
SN32	130.0	75.1	0	90.0	219740	1304592
SN33	130.0	75.1	0	90.0	545060	1304592
SN34	150.0	86.7	0	90.0	142810	154951
SN35	150.0	86.7	0	90.0	225260	154951

Table 3. Loading configurations and both experimental, N_{exp} , and estimated, N_{cal} , fatigue life values (run-outs are marked with *) for the specimens with a circular notch (root radius $\rho=2mm$).

TEST No.	σ [MPa]	τ [MPa]	R [-]	β [°]	N_{exp} [cycles]	N_{cal} [cycles]
CN1	170.0	98.1	-1	0.0	11042940	22609234
CN2	190.0	109.7	-1	0.0	6709756	4110592
CN3	190.0	109.7	-1	0.0	479740	4110592
CN4	210.0	121.2	-1	0.0	437192	499336
CN5	210.0	121.2	-1	0.0	199238	499336
CN6	250.0	144.3	-1	0.0	98800	79136
CN7	250.0	144.3	-1	0.0	137100	79136

CN8	270.0	155.9	-1	0.0	34714	15599
CN9	190.0	109.7	-1	90.0	1576358	3032736
CN10	190.0	109.7	-1	90.0	2000000*	3032736
CN11	210.0	121.2	-1	90.0	2110571*	288070
CN12	210.0	121.2	-1	90.0	83159	288070
CN13	250.0	144.3	-1	90.0	85106	47460
CN14	250.0	144.3	-1	90.0	106112	47460
CN15	140.0	80.8	0	0.0	496374	1783929
CN16	160.0	92.4	0	0.0	281725	553746
CN17	160.0	92.4	0	0.0	409673	553746
CN18	180.0	103.9	0	0.0	122489	145289
CN19	180.0	103.9	0	0.0	148534	145289
CN20	210.0	121.2	0	0.0	44537	41959
CN21	210.0	121.2	0	0.0	44441	41959
CN22	140.0	80.8	0	90.0	2028005*	3153778
CN23	160.0	92.4	0	90.0	266665	917719
CN24	160.0	92.4	0	90.0	365875	917719
CN25	180.0	103.9	0	90.0	160297	209747
CN26	180.0	103.9	0	90.0	110791	209747
CN27	210.0	121.2	0	90.0	79796	54364
CN28	210.0	121.2	0	90.0	88002	54364

Table 4. Loading configurations and both experimental, N_{exp} , and estimated, N_{cat} , fatigue life values (run-outs are marked with *) for the specimens with a blunt notch (root radius $\rho=5mm$).

TEST No.	σ [MPa]	τ [MPa]	R [-]	β [°]	N_{exp} [cycles]	N_{cat} [cycles]
BN1	200.0	115.4	-1	0.0	2032024*	6587263
BN2	230.0	132.7	-1	0.0	2000112*	1232409

BN3	230.0	132.7	-1	0.0	574035	1232409
BN4	260.0	150.0	-1	0.0	157459	280400
BN5	260.0	150.0	-1	0.0	900807	280400
BN6	290.0	167.4	-1	0.0	86359	74262
BN7	290.0	167.4	-1	0.0	55842	74262
BN8	260.0	150.0	-1	90.0	1339995	1186762
BN9	260.0	150.0	-1	90.0	2072946*	1186762
BN10	290.0	167.4	-1	90.0	205614	291757
BN11	290.0	167.4	-1	90.0	2026378*	291757
BN12	290.0	167.4	-1	90.0	168979	291757
BN13	315.0	181.9	-1	90.0	106169	99520
BN14	315.0	181.9	-1	90.0	76098	99520
BN15	160.0	92.4	0	0.0	2000493*	2024119
BN16	175.0	101.0	0	0.0	378650	705289
BN17	190.0	109.7	0	0.0	211696	267393
BN18	230.0	132.8	0	0.0	41058	27799
BN19	230.0	132.8	0	0.0	38522	27799
BN20	260.0	150.1	0	0.0	17556	6447
BN21	260.0	150.1	0	0.0	15954	6447
BN22	170.0	98.1	0	90.0	2009372*	1642638
BN23	170.0	98.1	0	90.0	2001122*	1642638
BN24	170.0	98.1	0	90.0	926366	1642638
BN25	180.0	103.9	0	90.0	311831	826027
BN26	180.0	103.9	0	90.0	544057	826027
BN27	200.0	115.4	0	90.0	171612	231694
BN28	200.0	115.4	0	90.0	106951	231694
BN29	250.0	144.3	0	90.0	53063	15225
BN30	250.0	144.3	0	90.0	43292	15225

Figure 4. Experimental, N_{exp} , vs estimated, N_{cal} , fatigue life for plain specimens No.: (a) T1-T8, (b) T9-T16, (c) T17-T24 and (d) T25-T32.

Table 5. T_{RMS} values related to both the present analytical methodology and the MWCM [17] for the plain specimens.

TEST No.	Loading type	T_{RMS} [-]	
		Present method.	MWCM [17]
T1-T8	Axial	1.37	1.46
T9-T16	Axial	1.66	1.67
T17-T24	Torsional	1.38	1.47
T25-T32	Biaxial	3.28	4.15
Overall (T1-T32)	-	1.98	2.25

Table 6. Stress concentration factors, K_t , for each test configuration examined.

Notch type	Loading type	K_t [-]
Sharp ($\rho = 0.07\text{ mm}$)	Axial	4.80
	Torsional	2.50
Circular ($\rho = 2\text{ mm}$)	Axial	1.75
	Torsional	1.30
Blunt ($\rho = 5\text{ mm}$)	Axial	1.30
	Torsional	1.12

Figure 5. Experimental, N_{exp} , vs estimated, N_{cal} , fatigue life for sharp notched (root radius $\rho=0.07mm$) specimens No.: (a) SN1-SN8, (b) SN9-SN15, (c) SN16-SN24, (d) SN25-SN28 and (e) SN29-SN35.

Figure 6. Experimental, N_{exp} , vs estimated, N_{cal} , fatigue life for circular notched (root radius $\rho=2mm$) specimens No.: (a) CN1-CN8, (b) CN9-CN14, (c) CN15-CN21 and (d) CN22-CN28.

Figure 7. Experimental, N_{exp} , vs estimated, N_{cal} , fatigue life for blunt notched (root radius $\rho=5mm$) specimens No.: (a) BN1-BN7, (b) BN8-BN14, (c) BN15-BN21 and (d) BN22-BN30.

Table 7. T_{RMS} values related to the present analytical methodology for the specimens with a sharp notch (test Nos. SN1-SN35), a circular notch (test Nos. CN1-CN28) and a blunt notch (test Nos. BN1-BN30).

TEST No.	T_{RMS} [-]	Overall
SN1-SN8	2.81	
SN9-SN15	3.42	
SN16-SN24	2.94	2.83
SN25-SN28	1.57	
SN29-SN35	2.86	
CN1-CN8	2.59	
CN9-CN14	2.36	2.21
CN15-CN21	1.76	
CN22-CN28	2.08	
BN1-BN7	1.99	
BN8-BN14	1.38	1.95
BN15-BN21	1.91	
BN22-BN30	2.29	